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Evaluation of the inhaled dose across different microenvironments

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Abstract. The principal aim of the INSIDE project (INDividual air pollution exposure, extracellular vesicles SIGNALing and hypertensive disorder DEVELOPMENT in pregnancy) is to assess the molecular effects of environmental exposure to airborne particulate matter (PM) of susceptible subject. Different approaches are considered to evaluate these effects, including an exposure-effect study performed on a selected population. The short-term exposure to different pollutants (PM and NO₂) was evaluated considering 51 subjects recruited from October 2017 to April 2018. Each subject was asked to carry personal instruments for few hours before a clinical evaluation (blood and cardiological examination) from home to hospital. Instruments used in the study were: (I) CairClip – CairPol (NO₂) and (II) Aerocet 831 - Aerosol Mass Monitor, Met One Instruments (size-fractionated PM). Moreover, a (III) smartphone with a GPS application and a (IV) Time Activity Diary (TAD) were used in this study to acquire information about the microenvironments (MEs) visited by subjects during the monitoring sessions.

The experimental design of the project allowed to further investigate issues related to the mode of exposure: through the analysis of TADs and GPS data, it was possible to document the time spent by each subject in the different MEs and characterize the average exposure and inhaled dose associated to different MEs.

The microenvironmental inhaled dose of pollutants was estimated considering the average exposure to PM and NO₂, the time spent across these MEs and the specific ventilation rate of each subject. Moreover, to understand which of these parameters has the major impact of the dose model, a sensitivity analysis was performed, on the total and on the MEs dataset.

1. Introduction

Travel microenvironments may represent sets of high exposure to air pollutants [1]. Despite the time spent commuting constitutes a small fraction of the whole day, it can be a significant contributor to total daily exposure.

Several studies have been carried out to assess the microenvironmental exposure of commuters across Europe [2][11], but most of these studies do not consider the dose inhaled by exposed subjects. As reported by Dons and collaborators [1], the inhaled dose is influenced by subject ventilation rate and by physical activity but, despite this, these parameters are often not considered and, as results, few studies are based on the evaluation of inhaled dose, especially during commuting.

In general, as reported by Betancourt et al. [12], most studies indicate that concentrations found in different means of transport are higher than those measured along pedestrian or cycling routes. It is recognized [13] that the factors that affect pollutant concentrations across different transportation modes are principally related to: (i) the travel mode (transport system, technology, energy source) and (ii) route characteristics (street configuration, micrometeorology, traffic). However, an additional aspect to consider is the possible difference between air pollution exposure and inhalation dose. As reported in [14], commuters that use passive transport, such as cars, train and subways are much exposed to air pollutants than commuters that use active transport (pedestrians or cyclists). Contrariwise, due to higher inhalation rate and higher time spent on road by active commuters, inhaled and deposited doses of pollutants are higher for active commuters.

The principal aim of this study is to evaluate the inhaled dose of pollutants across different MEs and the relative influence of input parameters on the dose estimates. The data used in this work were collected in the framework of the INSIDE project (INDividual air pollution exposure, extracellular vesicles SIGNALing and hypertensive disorders DEVELOPMENT in pregnancy).

2. Materials and Methods

The principal aim of the INSIDE project is to assess the molecular effects of environmental exposure to airborne particulate matter (PM) in susceptible subjects (pregnant women). To achieve this purpose, different approaches are considered including an exposure-effect study performed on a human population. The exposure assessment to different pollutants (PM and NO₂) was carried out on 51 pregnant women recruited during the winter 2017/18 (October 2017 - April 2018). The recruitment of 50 additional subjects is currently under way.

The enrolled subjects were asked to carry some portable instruments (Figure 1) for the measurement of air concentrations in the breathing zone while moving to the hospital for the clinical evaluation on routes not fixed a priori. The monitoring period and route length was not fixed a priori but was variable according to the habits of enrolled subjects and to the clinical evaluation time. Personal measurements were performed once for each subject enrolled.

Figure 1. Instruments used in the study: (a): measurement instrumentation as worn by a subject; (b): Aerocet; (c): CC; (d): mobile phone.

The measurement of NO₂ concentration were performed using an electrochemical miniaturized monitor (CairClip NO₂, Cairpol; La Roche Blanche – France – named “CC” – Figure 1(c)) and the continuous monitoring of PM concentrations was achieved via a portable direct reading monitor (Aerocet 831-MetOne Instrument Inc., Grant Pass, Oregon, USA – named “Aerocet” – Figure 1(b)) that provided concentration data of size-fractionated PM (PM₁, PM_{2.5}, PM₄, PM₁₀ and TSP). To improve the data quality, comparative sessions between a freshly calibrated Aerocet and a gravimetric gold standard for PM_{2.5} (Harvard Impactor MS&T Area Sampler Diagnostic and Engineering, Inc., Harrison, ME, USA, named here as “HI”) were carried out. Both CC and Aerocet were set with an acquisition rate equal to 1 minute. In order to track and record the position of subjects during the

monitoring sessions, a mobile phone (LG K4 2017 – Figure 1(d)), provided with an Android application (GEO TRACKER – GPS TRACKER; Version 3.3.0) was used and set with an acquisition rate of 30s and a precision of 200m. As a support for the reconstruction of the routes and frequented microenvironments, volunteers were asked to complete a Time Activity Diary (TAD).

The inhaled dose was estimated using 3 parameters: personal exposure, time fraction spent across different MEs and individual ventilation rate (VE). In this study individual VE has been measured during the clinical evaluation and reported as resting or warm-up ventilation. Values referred to the resting ventilation has been considered as VE during passive activities (indoor environments and passive commuting) while warm-up values were used to estimate the inhaled dose during active transport (walking or cycling).

To assess how much VE, time spent in MEs and exposure concentrations affect the inhaled dose, a sensitivity analysis was performed.

3. Results

Average time spent across different MEs is reported in Figure 2. On average, 69% of time has been spent in indoor environments, while only 1% in an outdoor environment. 30% of time has been spent commuting and in detail the major part of the travel has been spent on private transport (i.e., car – 34%) and moving by foot (30%). The time spent concerning the use of underground was equal to 17%, while time spent in train, tram, bike and bus was respectively equal to 6%, 6%, 4% and 3%.

Figure 2. Time spent across different MEs.

In Table 1, the average exposure concentrations and individual inhaled dose are reported for PM_{2.5} and NO₂, considering different MEs.

Table 1. Mean concentration and subject inhaled dose (*) for PM_{2.5} and NO₂ across different ME (μg/m³).

MEs	Tram	Train	Metro	Bus	Car	Walking	Bike	Outdoor	Indoor	Hospital	Home
PM _{2.5}	42.3 *7.5	15.2 *11.0	36.8 *9.2	23.8 *5.6	23.7 *10.1	26.3 *8.2	18.5 *18.5	28.4 *5.9	19.5 *23.8	14.8 *7.3	19.40 *17.8
NO ₂	65.7 *24.9	47.6 *13.8	42.2 *22.4	69.7 *17.6	69.9 *30.7	64.9 *21.9	65.9 *65.3	61.5 *14.1	46.0 *30.0	62.4 *27.3	54.1 *22.4

Concentration data were combined with the time spent by subject across MEs and pulmonary ventilation rate (VE), calculated or measured for each subject, to estimate the inhaled dose of pollutants for each subject in each ME visited. Results of sensitivity analysis are reported in Figure 3. The sensitivity analysis was performed changing single variables (concentration, ventilation rate and time spent across different microenvironment) and considering minimum, maximum and mean value for the calculation of estimated inhaled dose. From the graph is clear that the time spent in a ME is an influent parameter for the dose, followed by personal exposure and by personal ventilation rate.

Figure 3. Sensitivity analysis performed considering personal exposure (μg/m³), time spent across different MEs (minutes) and the ventilation rate of subjects (m³/min).

As reported in Figure 3, the parameters having the major impact on the inhaled dose are the time spent in a ME and personal exposure. VE seems to have a low impact on the inhaled dose, both for MEs and kind of pollutant.

Personal exposure has the major impact during active commuting (walking and cycling), even if these results are not in agreement with Zuurbier and collaborators [11]. In their work is reported how VE is the parameter that influence more the inhaled dose, since with the physical effort the VE increase.

Also, regarding the passive transport considered in this study (car, bus, metro, train and tram), it is possible to identify that personal exposure most influences the inhaled dose.

4. Conclusions

The aim of this study is to evaluate the inhaled dose of PM_{2.5} and NO₂ across different MEs and in particular during commuting, since most literature usually report only the exposure assessment to different pollutant and not results regarding the inhaled dose.

Analyzing pollutants concentration, time fraction spent across different MEs and the subject VE, the inhaled dose was calculated. Moreover, via sensitivity analysis, it has been observed that the most influence parameter on the dose value is the time spent in a ME, followed by personal exposure.

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